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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CATEGORY OF CASE IN THE GEORGIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Annotation. The paper concerns the category of case and the comparative analysis of its forms in the Georgian and English languages.

The paper reviews the grammatical category, classification of affixes (prefix, suffix, infix) and their functions. It also describes the case as a grammatical category in the Georgian and English languages, its functions and its comparison to the Genitive case of the Georgian language. It describes postpositional case in the Georgian language but in the English language it's called prepositional. About this issue, an analysis was made on the basis of Georgian and English examples.

Key Words: Case, grammar, comparison, stem

The system of the case of names in the Georgian language was the same: all common names had one rule of case; they used the same sign of case. This rule is currently maintained in plural where all the stems have final consonant. The difference between the names in plural can be that some stems undergo changes (contracted or shortened), and the forms of all the nouns are derived in the same way. Consequently, case as a morphological process is one in the plural. Therefore, considering the inflection, the nouns are not divided into groups in the plural.

The signs of case in the singular are preserved only in the forms of nouns with a final consonant without postpositions. In the nouns with the final vowel, the signs of case change their form.

According to the signs of case, the nouns in the singular are divided into two large groups: the first group includes the names that have unchanged signs of case; these are the nouns with a final consonant; the second group comprises the nouns that do not have unchanged signs of case; these are the nouns with a final vowel. Based on this, we have two types of case in the Georgian language: I and II. Names with final consonants belong to the first type of case, and names with final vowels belong to the second case.

Name of people the stem of which ends in a consonant are all unstemmed. Two things distinguish them from the case of common nouns in modern literary Georgian language: for example, nominative, “Zaal (Zaal – i) had gone out on the balcony early in the morning and looking over the groves” (Tsereteli, A. “Bashi – Achuki”).

Genitive: “Manager, - said Zaal, do you understand? Why are you hesitating?” (Tsereteli, A. “Bashi – Achuki”).

Vocative: “– Darejan!... – said Luarsab with a broken heart and shyness.” (Chavchavadze, I. “Katsia Adamiani”).

In the English language, the form of noun case is a morphologically conjugative form which unlike Georgian has two types of case: possessive case (-‘s, -‘, -of), which is traditionally known as “Genitive” and Common case (Volkona, L. M.). The function of the apostrophe – ‘s is to distinguish the singular noun in the possessive case from the plural noun in the common case, for example., a) “Close by Miss Temple’s bed, and half covered with its white curtains, there stood a little crib”; b) “And then they had called her to a sofa, where she now sat, ensconced between them, chattering alternately in French and broken English; absorbing not only the young ladies’ attention, but that of Mrs. Eshton and Lady Lynn, and getting spoilt to her heart’s content”; c) “I involuntarily split half the contents of my cup into my saucer, I did not choose to consider” (Charlotte Bronte, “Jane Eyre”).

Functionally, “the forms of case” of the English nouns are related to each other in a very peculiar way. This peculiarity lies in the fact that the common form is absolutely indefinite in a semantic point of view, while the form of Genitive has restricted functions. Thus, common case has the ability to express the semantics of genitive (namely, in a contact and in a prepositional collocation) that will turn the entire case of Genitive into an auxiliary element in the grammatical system of an English noun (Blokh, 1983), for example, “**The bringing of** the accusation against the Widow Capet appears desirable, taking into consideration the mood of the City of Paris”.

Thus, in addition to genitive case, the noun in the English language, just like Latin grammar, has a non – conjugative, i.e. pure positional cases: nominative, vocative, dative and accusative. For example, nominative (subject in relation to the verb) – Creatures absorbed; vocative – Little friend! said he, in quite a changed tone; dative (indirect object in relation to the verb) - “Miss Miller signed to me to sit on a bench near the door”; accusative (direct object and a prepositional object as well) - “ I read these words over and over”; “My attention was now called off by Miss Smith” (Charlotte Bronte, “Jane Eyre”).

Although nouns in English have only one form of case (genitive), they take a variety of inflections in a sentence with the help of prepositions and particles. So, for example, let’s compare the noun given in all cases in the Georgian language to the form it takes in the English language.

1. Nominative (singular) – “ცხენი სულ ახლოს იყო, მაგრამ ჯერ კიდევ არ ჩანდა”; “The horse was very near, but not yet in sight”. (plural.). – “ცხენოსნები გასახვევისაკენ გაემართნენ, სწრაფადაც შეუხვიეს იქვე სახლის კუთხეში”; “The horsemen, following the sweep of the drive, quickly turned the angle of the house”.

2. Ergative – “მისტერ როჩესტერმა ალბათ შენიშნა ჩვენი შესვლა ოთახში, მაგრამ, როგორც ჩანდა, სრულიადაც არ იყო გუნებაზე ჩვენთვის ყურადღება

მოქცია”; **“Mr. Rochester must have been aware of the entrance of us, but it appeared he was not in the mood to notice us”**.

3. Dative/accusative – “უკვე ცხრა საათია. რას ფიქრობთ, მის ეარ, ადელს ნებას აძლევთ ამდენ ხანს აქ იჯდეს?”; “It’s nine o’clock: what are you about, Miss Eyre, to let **Adele** sit up so long?” (dative). “**ადელი** ფანჯარას მივარდა”; “**Adele** flew to the window” (accusative).

4. Genitive – “მისტერ ჯონის სიკვდილის ამბავი ისე მოულოდნელად მივიღეთ, რომ ელდა ეცა და სამი დღე ენაჩავარდნილი იყო”; “The information about Mr. John’s death and the manner of it came too suddenly: it brought on a stroke”.

5. Instrumental – “ეს დანით არ უნდა იყოს გაჭრილი, უფრო კბილებითაა დაგლეჯილი”; “This wound was not done **with a knife**: there have been teeth here”.

6. Adverbial – “აბა, რა საქმე გაქვს თორნფილდის პატრონთან, შენ მხოლოდ ხელფასს ღებულობ მისტერ როჩესტერის შვილობილის აღსაზრდელად”; “You have nothing to do with the master of Thornifield, further than to receive the salary he gives you **for teaching** his protégée”.

7. Vocative – “აბა, **ჯონ**, გამოჩნდნენ?”; “Well, **John**, any news?”.

8. (Charlotte Bronte, “Jane Eyre”).

As we see from the examples, the genitive (possessive) case of the English language is the only one which is followed by a case particle and corresponds to the genitive case of the Georgian language, and in the remaining cases the stem is the same and expresses the case with various prepositions. For example, in an instrumental case, the case sign “-ით” is reflected in English with the preposition “with”.

Thus, the research enables us to formulate the following theoretical generalizations:

- Following differences were revealed when considering the case as a category in the English and Georgian languages: according to the Georgian Grammar, the situation does not change even if we change the place of the word, for example, “ქვრივი ვენახს ძალიან კარგად უვლიდა” და “ვენახს ქვრივი ძალიან კარგად უვლიდა” – in both cases the word “widow” (ქვრივი) is a subject (nominative case), and “vineyard” (ვენახი) is an object (dative case). We got an absolutely different result in the English language: the subject turned into an object, for example: “Children had finished the breakfast” და “The breakfast had been finished by children”.

- When comparing the case system according to the parts of speech, it was determined that in addition to genitive case, the English language has other cases as well (nominative, vocative, dative and accusative), which are not conjugated, i.e. they are not followed by the signs of case: “I repeated these words over and over” – here the noun is reflected in the dative case.

This brief research makes it visible how important the role of comparative – typological method is in identifying linguistic universals and differences between languages.

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